

Portfolio Modeling Through Sentiment Analysis using Plutchik's Wheel

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ABSTRACT

With the emergence of powerful computing systems, efforts are being made to analyse, capture and predict the trends in which the market will move. Various paradigms such as neural networks, are being heavily implemented to predict the prices of stocks by taking into account various features that may influence it. In this paper, the authors propose a mathematical model that implements sentiment analysis as one of the features through which buy and sell signals are generated for a particular stock. The closing prices of a stock for the time periods are fetched and is correlated with extracted emotion. An effort is made to capture the trend of sentiment towards the stock and BUY/SELL signals are generated depending on the strength of the captured trend. Along with the sentiment, the Exponential Moving Average (EMA) for the stocks are also computed and curve fitted in a 3 degree polynomial which allows us to implement another filter for determining the amount of shares that can be bought or sold depending on the expected EMA growth, volatility of the stock and allowed risk exposure at that point of time.

Keywords- Sentiment Analysis, Algorithmic Trading, Automated Trading, Stock Market Prediction, Mathematical Model

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increase in computing power and the ability to harness larger, more complex amount of data, the investing paradigm has shifted drastically from fundamental to quantitative. Instead of not only analyzing revenue, cash flow etc. analysts are now also using features such as complex mathematical models, statistical variables and regression analysis. Recently there is a trend of combining fundamental factors and quantitative factors for asset selection. This is termed as “quantimental investing”. Through this, clients have a potential to generate higher returns by implementing the best of both the tactics [1].

One of the features being used in prediction of stock trends is the sentiment of the general public towards a particular company and towards the market as a whole. Sentiment analysis along with other indicators are being widely used to make buy and sell decisions automatically. Twitter has been a major source of texts on which sentiment analysis is performed as tweets are of limited length and of a particular structure which makes analyzing and classification easier. Smailović et. al. (2013) studied financial tweets of eight companies and concluded that changes in positive sentiment probability was able to predict similar movement in closing price of stocks [2]. Many more such studies were performed on texts extracted from twitter which are discussed in the literature review section.

Dedicated computer programs termed black-boxes use various inputs to generate investment strategies. These Black-Box financial models are nothing but a computer program that churns out investment strategies as output by considering various data as input. The main characteristic is that the internal working of the program is completely hidden.

Figure 1

The deployment of these black boxes has made indulging in trading an automated process. The implemented algorithm generates BUY/SELL signals based on predefined parameters, manages risk and makes automated trade executions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are various studies performed to correlate public sentiments and movements in stock prices. Pagolu et. al. (2016) developed a sentiment analyzer that classifies the sentiment of the tweet as positive, negative and neutral. They claimed that positive sentiment of public towards a company was reflected in its price [3]. Rao and Srivastava (2012) analyzed 4 million tweets for DJIA, NASDAQ-100 and 13 tech stocks and found high correlation (0.88) between stock prices and sentiment extracted [4]. Makrehchi et. al. (2013) extracted significant stock movements and collected relevant texts from social media. By assigning a positive or negative label to the collected tweets, they trained a model to predict the label of future tweets. They showed that the net sentiment had a significant predictive power for determining stock movements and created trading strategies based on the system which provided significant returns. Their trading strategy was able to beat S&P500 by about 20% in 4 months [5]. Nguyen and Shirai (2015) proposed topic-sentiment feature for stock market prediction model. Their model termed "TSLDA" captured the topic and sentiment simultaneously. Their method is 56% accurate in predicting stock trends [6]. Mittal and Goel (2012) [7] advanced the technique proposed by Bollen et al. [8], where they implemented a combination of sentiment analysis and machine learning to find a correlation between public sentiment and market sentiment. Like most of the previous studies mentioned, they also used twitter data to predict the public's mood. The twitter data was clustered with a degree of membership into 4 clusters: calm, happy, alert and kind. The mood, along with the previous day's DJIA values was used to predict future stock movements. They achieved a 75.56% accuracy result using k-fold sequential cross validation.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this paper we propose a portfolio risk management mathematical model based on sentiment analysis of relevant texts. The risk exposure is controlled by manipulating the position size of stocks in the portfolio. The proposed model throws a BUY/SELL signal by correlating the fetched stock price with extracted public sentiment and then predicting the sentiment through curve fitting. The amount to be bought depends on the allowed risk exposure and expected EMA gain of the stock along with its volatility. Plutchik's Wheel of Emotion is used for analyzing and classifying sentiments. We have considered that there is no slippage and the market is assumed to be frictionless.

4. PROPOSED MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The model is divided into the following sections:

4.1 Extraction of Emotion from Text

The first objective of our proposed model is to perform sentiment analysis on relevant texts. For sentiment analysis and classification, we are referring to Plutchik's Wheel of Emotion model. Figure 2 below shows the diagram of the wheel.

Figure 2

The Plutchik's Wheel of Emotion is an emotion classification model proposed by Robert Plutchik in the year 1980. It has 8 basic emotions which are arranged according to their opposite polarity. These are, {joy, sadness}, {anger, fear}, {trust, distrust} and {surprise, anticipation}. As we move towards the middle of the wheel, the intensities of the emotions increase. For instance, rage is a high intensity anger. According to the model, the basic emotions can be mixed to form other emotions, such as, remorse is an emotion which is formed by combining disgust and sadness.

For extracting the emotion from the text, we are proposing an algorithm inspired from emotion summering method proposed by Abbasi and Beltiukov (2019). The model gives the emotions in the wheel some weights. The centremost emotions, which is the most intense form, like rage is given a weight 4 and as we move outward, the values decrease by 1. The text is analysed for occurrence of such emotions and total occurrence is noted down. Let the total occurrence of emotion e_i

be x_i . x_i is multiplied with the corresponding emotion's weight to compute the intensity of the emotion I_{ei} [9].

$$I_{ei} = x_i \times w_i \quad - (1)$$

For instance, if we look at the following phrase: “*the game by company X is quite boring which made its audience sad*”. We see that for the phrase we get 2 emotional intensities, Sadness and Disgust (Boredom's base emotion is disgust). Hence, $I_{e(sad)} = 3$ and $I_{e(disgust)} = 2$. However, sadness and disgust together form a complex emotion, that is remorse. We propose algorithm1 for dissolving the base emotions into complex ones where-ever applicable.

ALGORITHM 1: Complex Emotions
<p>FOR any 2 adjacent emotions e_i and e_j if $I_{ei} - I_{ej} \leq 1$ initiate $e_k \leftarrow e_i \cap e_j$ $I_{ek} = \frac{I_{ei} + I_{ej}}{2}$ Delete e_i & e_j END</p>

Applying algorithm1 on Text1 we get $e_k = \text{remorse}$ and $I_{ek} = 2.5$.

Once all the possible base emotions have been dissolved into complex ones, the emotions extracted are used to update the Net-emotion/sentiment about the company/stock.

4.2 Net-Emotion about a Company/Stock

The emotion extracted from relevant texts updates the cumulative sentiment towards the company. Let \mathcal{E}_k be the current cumulative intensity of emotion k . The value of \mathcal{E}_k is updated as $\mathcal{E}_{k(updated)} = \mathcal{E}_k + I_k$, where I_k is the intensity of emotion k extracted from a text.

In our model, we are considering {joy, trust, optimism, love} as positive polarity, {Sadness, Disgust, Anger, Submission, Disapproval, Remorse, Contempt, Aggressiveness, Fear} as negative polarity and {Surprise, Awe, Anticipation} as neutral sentiment. The total sum of positive intensity, negative intensity and neutral intensity is represented by equation (2), (3) and (4) respectively.

$$\mathbb{X}_{pos} = \sum_{i=1}^4 \phi_i \mathcal{E}_i \quad - (2)$$

$$\mathbb{X}_{neg} = \sum_{w=1}^9 \phi_w \mathcal{E}_w \quad - (3)$$

$$\mathbb{X}_{neu} = \sum_{j=1}^3 \phi_j \mathcal{E}_j \quad - (4)$$

In the above equations, ϕ is the dependency coefficient on a particular emotion which in our case is taken as $\frac{1}{m}$ where m is the number of emotions in that polarity.

4.3 Trivial Position Sizing in Investing

The total risk endurance on the principle amount along with the predetermined stop-loss value is used to determine the number of shares to buy i.e. the size of a position inside a portfolio.

Let the principle amount for stock option i be P_i , the entry point be E_i and the predetermined stop-loss amount be SL_i . Let the percentage of risk endurance be denoted by \mathbb{R} , then the number of shares (N_i) we can buy of stock i to stay inside our risk parameter is:

$$N_i = \frac{\mathbb{R}\% \times P_i}{E_i - SL_i} \quad - (5)$$

It can be rewritten as

$$N_i(E_i - SL_i) = \mathbb{R}\% \times P_i \quad - (6)$$

The total risk exposure of a portfolio containing n number of stock options can be written as the summation of their individual risk exposure.

$$Risk_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i(E_i - SL_i) \quad - (7)$$

However, in our model we require the ratio of risk exposure to total principle amount which will serve as the upper limit of risk exposure at all buying times. Suppose the ratio is \hat{R} then the ratio of risk to valuation of our portfolio during the buy phase must be $\leq \hat{R}$.

4.4 Correlating Price and Extracted Sentiment

The first step in the model is to find the Pearson's Correlation coefficient between the Price of a stock and sentiment extracted towards the stock. To achieve this, we consider a time interval Δt and a look back time T_{lb} . T_{lb} is a time period for which historical data (price and sentiment) is available and $T_{lb} = w\Delta t, w \in \mathbb{Z}: w \in [10, \infty)$, implying that the look-back time is a multiple of Δt . The price (equation8) and the Net positive emotion towards a company(equation9) is computed and Pearson's correlation formula is used (equation10).

$$M(price) = Price_{\Delta t} \quad - (8)$$

$$Enet_{(\Delta t)} = \mathbb{X}_{pos(\Delta t)} - \mathbb{X}_{neg(\Delta t)} \quad - (9)$$

$$\rho_{M \sim E} = \frac{\sum((M - \bar{M})(Enet_{(\Delta t)} - \overline{Enet_{(\Delta t)}}))}{\sqrt{\sum(M - \bar{M})^2 \sum(Enet_{(\Delta t)} - \overline{Enet_{(\Delta t)}})^2}} \quad - (10)$$

In the above equation, \bar{M} and $\overline{Enet_{(\Delta t)}}$ are the mean of price and net emotion respectively. The value of Pearson's correlation coefficient lies between -1 and 1. A value closer to -1 or 1 denotes that $Enet_{(\Delta t)}$ & $M(price)$ are strongly correlated while a value closer to 0 means that there is little to no relation between them.

4.5 Exponential Moving Average

Exponential Moving Average (EMA) of a stock price is one of the common technical indicators to determine buy and sell signals. The EMA is generally used instead of Simple Moving Average (SMA) because it provides smoother results than SMA for a fixed time frame [10].

The main distinction between EMA and SMA is that, the EMA gives recent prices more weight compared to historical prices whereas in SMA, all the prices are given the equal amount of weightage. This helps to capture the trend more efficiently. The formula for EMA is as follows:

$$EMA = ((ClosePrice - EMA_{prev}) \times \Omega) + EMA_{prev} \quad - (11)$$

Where $\Omega = \frac{2}{k}$ and k is the number of time periods. Since the current EMA value is calculated using previous EMA values, therefore initially, the SMA is taken as the first EMA value. SMA is the simple average of the prices in the time period.

$$SMA = \frac{P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + \dots + P_k}{k} \quad - (12)$$

In our proposed model, we are considering $\frac{w\Delta t}{2}$ as the length of the time period for which EMA is computed.

The following algorithms depict the process for updating the EMA values of a particular stock.

ALGORITHM 2: Fetch Price

```

A[] ← List of prices of the stock
Avail_price(){
    Try{
        Pi = Fetch price from API
        A[] ← Append Pi
        Signal = TRUE
    }
    Except{
        Signal = FALSE
    }
    Return Signal
}

```

The above algorithm is used to fetch prices of a particular stock from APIs and is inserted into a list A[]. If the algorithm successfully fetches the price, then Signal is set to true else it is set to false.

Algorithm3 below shows the instruction for computing the SMA which acts as the initial EMA value.

ALGORITHM 3: Compute SMA

```

Cal_init_SMA(){
  j = 1
  n =  $\frac{w}{2}$ 
  while (j ≤ n){
    Sig ← Avail_price()
    If(Sig = TRUE){
      j++
      wait( $\Delta t$ )
    }
    Else {wait( $\Delta t$ )}
  }
  For(i=0; i < n; i++){
    SMA = SMA + A[i]
  }
  SMA=SMA/n
}

```

The Cal_init_SMA() function calls the Avail_price() function $\frac{w}{2}$ times. Hence, $w/2$ number of elements(prices) are inserted in list A[]. Once we have the required number of elements, the average is computed which serves as the SMA. Once the SMA is calculated, the EMA needs to be computed after every time interval of Δt . We propose a recursive function Cal_EMA() for this purpose. Cal_EMA() calls the Avail_price() function and computes the EMA for the fetched price. It waits for a time period of Δt and calls itself again. By using this recursive function, the EMA value keeps on getting updated for the continuously fetched price.

ALGORITHM 4: Compute EMA

```

l = 1
Cal_EMA(){
  l = l + 1
  S ← Avail_price()
  If(S=TRUE){
     $EMA_l = ((a[l] - SMA) \times \Omega) + SMA$ 
    SMA =  $EMA_l$ 
    Wait( $\Delta t$ )
    Cal_EMA(l)
  }
  Else {
    Wait( $\Delta t$ )
    Cal_EMA(l)
  }
}
}

```

The Cal_EMA() function is called after the computation of Cal_init_SMA(). The function calls Avail_price() which returns TRUE if it successfully fetches the price from API. The EMA value is calculated with the latest fetched price and the SMA value is updated to the current computed EMA value. The algorithm waits for a period of Δt and recursively calls itself again. If the Avail_price() function signals

FALSE i.e. it was unable to fetch the price from API, then the algorithm waits for a period of Δt and calls itself again. Therefore, through algorithm4, the EMA is continuously updated.

4.6 Making the Prediction

For the prediction phase, we are implementing curve fitting techniques. The goal is not to predict the price with pin point accuracy, but rather capture the trend in which the stock prices will move.

We are implementing least square fit method for the curve fitting. The objective function is given as

$$E_2 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum (\hat{Y} - Y)^2} \quad - (13)$$

Where \hat{Y} represents the curve.

For predicting the Sentiment, we are using a linear fit (eq. 14) and for EMA we are using 3rd degree polynomial curve (eq. 15)

$$\hat{Y} = A_l x + B_l \quad - (14)$$

$$\hat{Y} = A_c x^3 + B_c x^2 + C_c x + D_c \quad - (15)$$

For computing A_l and B_l , we create objective function $E_2' = \sum (\hat{Y} - Y)^2$ and minimize the function by computing $\frac{\partial E_2'}{\partial A_l} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial E_2'}{\partial B_l} = 0$. The resulting equations are represented in matrix form as follows.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sum x^2 & \sum x \\ \sum x & n \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_l \\ B_l \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum xy \\ \sum y \end{pmatrix}$$

Similarly, for the 3rd degree polynomial we get the following matrix system

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sum x^6 & \sum x^5 & \sum x^4 & \sum x^3 \\ \sum x^5 & \sum x^4 & \sum x^3 & \sum x^2 \\ \sum x^4 & \sum x^3 & \sum x^2 & \sum x \\ \sum x^3 & \sum x^2 & \sum x & n \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_c \\ B_c \\ C_c \\ D_c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum yx^3 \\ \sum yx^2 \\ \sum yx \\ \sum y \end{pmatrix}$$

Solving the matrix system, we get the coefficients and the intercept for our polynomial curve. Since we have divided the time into time period Δt , therefore if T represents the current time period, then we can use our polynomial curves to predict the values at $T + n\Delta t$, where $n \in \{1,2,3 \dots\}$

4.7 BUY and SELL Signals

Let our portfolio be denoted as \mathbb{U} , which is made up of various assets Φ_n .

$$\mathbb{U} = \{\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \Phi_3, \Phi_4 \dots \Phi_k\}$$

The valuation of the portfolio can be divided into 2 parts, i.e. Liquid and Assets. Liquids denote the buying capacity and is riskless with no growth while assets are risky and have growth.

Figure 3

The total valuation is the sum of liquid and asset at that point of time.

$$V_U = L_T + \mathcal{A}_T \quad - (16)$$

Where \mathcal{A}_T is the total valuation of all the stocks at time T.

During BUY phase the risk exposure from \mathcal{A}_T must be less than or equal to \hat{R} .

The BUY or SELL signals are dependent on the predicted sentiment value. The first step is to filter out stocks for which we do not have a strong enough correlation between extracted sentiment and price. We are considering that the Pearson's coefficient calculated must be ≥ 0.6 and R^2 value (coefficient of determination) for the linearly fitted line for sentiment prediction must be ≥ 0.5 . The assets passing these criteria are checked for BUY or SELL action. The stocks which fail to meet the criterion are not tradable through this sentiment analysed model as this particular model fails to capture the trend for those stocks.

$$\rho_{M \sim E} \geq 0.6 \ \&\& \ R^2(\text{Linear Fit}) \geq 0.5 \quad - (Cr. 1)$$

Let the predicted Net extracted Emotion towards a stock (equation9) for the current time period T and the next time period $T + \Delta t$ be denoted as $\hat{Y}_{Enet(T)}$ and $\hat{Y}_{Enet(T+\Delta t)}$ respectively. Since at any point of time t, we have limited liquid L_t which depicts the total buying capacity at that time, therefore, we prioritize all the stocks that pass criteria Cr. 1 using their φ_{ϕ_i} values.

$$\varphi_{\phi_i} = (\hat{Y}_{Enet(T+\Delta t)} - \hat{Y}_{Enet(T)})(R^2)(\rho_{M \sim E}) \quad - (17)$$

Using the φ_{ϕ_i} value, the preliminary BUY and SELL signals are generated as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IF } \varphi_{\phi_i} > 0: & \text{Prelim BUY Signal} \\ \text{IF } \varphi_{\phi_i} < 0: & \text{Prelim SELL Signal} \end{aligned}$$

Because of criteria 1 (Cr. 1), the value of $(R^2)(\rho_{M \sim E})$ is always positive and hence the prelim decision depends on the value of $(\hat{Y}_{Enet(T+\Delta t)} - \hat{Y}_{Enet(T)})$, which is basically the slope of the linear fitted line. A positive slope along with strong enough coefficient of determination and correlation would result in a BUY, while a negative slope with similar conditions would result in a SELL.

For illustrative purposes consider a hypothetical company III, on which the model is being implemented. From relevant sources we are getting the net emotion (equation9) for the company for every time period Δt . Consider that the distribution is as the following plot.

Figure 4

Assuming that the correlation coefficient between the price and extracted sentiment is high ($\rho_{M \sim E} \geq 0.6$) for the lookback time, then the BUY/SELL is dependent on the linear fit. Taking the value of $n = 24$ for linear fit computation, for our data points we get the following pattern.

Figure 5

Every time we get a positive value of $(\hat{Y}_{Enet(T+\Delta t)} - \hat{Y}_{Enet(T)})$ along with $R^2(\text{Linear Fit}) \geq 0.5$ a BUY is triggered while a negative value along with a strong $R^2(\text{Linear Fit})$ will trigger a SELL. For example, the following set of plots (Figure6) show 3 such cases where the model triggers a SELL, BUY and Indeterminable case.

For generating the confirmation BUY/SELL, which acts as an additional filter, the first component we require is the updated STOPLOSS value. Let us denote it as SL_U . The logic behind updated STOPLOSS is that for a particular stock there can be multiple BUY signals at different points of time. When a BUY signal is actually executed, the stoploss value of all the shares bought (current + previously bought) of the particular stock is updated with the latest calculated one.

While there are various sophisticated methods for calculation of stoplosses, simple support levels are mostly used in determining stoplosses because in general, when the stock breaks through the support level, it tends to move downwards.

Hence, in our model also, the support level plays the role in determination of the updated stoploss value.

Figure 6

With the updated Stoploss, the following value of μ is calculated for stock Φ_i .

$$\mu = \frac{\zeta}{(C_T - SL_U)} \times \text{Signof}(\hat{Y}_{EMA(T)} - \hat{Y}_{EMA(T+\Delta t)}) \quad - (18)$$

$$\zeta = \frac{\sum (E_p - SL_U) (N_{E_p})}{\sum N_{E_p}} \quad - (19)$$

There can be multiple time points of entry for a certain stock and hence there can be multiple entry point values (E_p) for it. This is the reason why the average is taken. The notation N_{E_p} denotes the number of shares bought at entry point E_p . The C_T denotes the current share price of the stock and $(\hat{Y}_{EMA(T)} - \hat{Y}_{EMA(T+\Delta t)})$ denotes the difference between predicted EMA at time T and predicted EMA at time T+ Δt .

For the confirmation SELL trigger, the value of μ must be positive and less than 1. The positive value denotes that the EMA would go down according to the 3-degree curve fit and a value less than 1 would denote that the $(C_T - SL_U)$ component is greater than ζ .

IF $\mu < 1$ && $\mu > 0$:

Confirm SELL(Amount)

Where Amount $\approx \frac{\text{Volatility of } \phi}{C_T - SL_U} \times N_\phi$

For example, let us consider two stocks ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , both of which has received a prelim SELL signal.

NAME	ϕ_1
E_1	30
E_2	20
SL_U	18
C_T	28
N_{E_1}	4
N_{E_2}	6

For ϕ_1 , the ζ value using equation 19 is:

$$\zeta = \frac{(30 - 18)(4) + (20 - 18)(6)}{10} = 6$$

The value of $\mu = \frac{\zeta}{(C_T - SL_U)}$ is:

$$\mu = \frac{6}{28 - 18} = 0.6$$

Therefore, if the sign of $(\hat{Y}_{EMA(T)} - \hat{Y}_{EMA(T+\Delta t)})$ is positive, then a Confirm SELL signal is given by the model. The number of shares to be sold is determined by:

$$Amount \approx \frac{Volatility\ of\ \phi_1}{C_T - SL_U} \times N_{\phi_1} \quad - (20)$$

NAME	ϕ_2
E_1	20
E_2	22
E_3	16
SL_U	12
C_T	18
N_{E_1}	5
N_{E_2}	3
N_{E_3}	2

Similarly, for ϕ_2 , the ζ value using equation 19 is:

$$\zeta = \frac{(20 - 12)(5) + (22 - 12)(3) + (16 - 12)(2)}{10} = 7.8$$

The value of $\mu = \frac{\zeta}{(C_T - SL_U)}$ is:

$$\mu = \frac{7.8}{18 - 12} = 1.3$$

Therefore, even if the sign of $(\hat{Y}_{EMA(T)} - \hat{Y}_{EMA(T+\Delta t)})$ is positive, the Confirm SELL signal would not be given and the shares would be kept in the portfolio for the time period. However, in accordance to the Stoploss definition, the shares of a stock are sold off automatically if the current price hits the Stoploss value.

The following set of plots show the SELL decision derived from curve fitting for the hypothetical company III at the time period $T=24\Delta t$.

Figure 7

The above plot gives a visual representation of the curve fits done by the model on the net extracted sentiment and the Exponential Moving Average in the time period $T=24\Delta t$. The curve fits trigger a sell response for the stocks but the final confirmed SELL trigger would also depend on the value of μ .

After selling and updating the Stoploss values of the relevant stocks, the new risk exposure value is computed. The risk from the stocks under current portfolio holding can be denoted by the following equation.

$$\mathcal{R}_k = \sum_{\Phi_k} \left(\sum \left((E_{p(t_j)} - SL_U) \left(N_{\Phi(t_j)} \right) \right) \right) \quad - (21)$$

$$\forall E_{p(t_j)} > SL_U, N_{\Phi(t_j)} > 0$$

For instance, the risk exposure due to stocks Φ_1 and Φ_2 from the previous example is:

$$\mathcal{R}_{\Phi_1} = (30 - 18)(4) + (20 - 18)(6) = 60$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\Phi_2} = (20 - 12)(5) + (22 - 12)(3) + (16 - 12)(2) = 78$$

Therefore, the total risk due to both of them is $\mathcal{R}_k = \mathcal{R}_{\Phi_1} + \mathcal{R}_{\Phi_2} = 138$.

As stated in section 4.3, the risk exposure must be less than or equal to \hat{R} . Let $R_{(Tot)(init)}$ be the initial total risk, V_{init} be the initial valuation of our portfolio, V_u be the current valuation and R_{max} be the current maximum allowed risk exposure. Then by definition, R_{max} is

$$R_{max} = \frac{R_{(Tot)(init)}}{V_{init}} \times V_u \quad - (22)$$

Hence, during the BUY phase of the model, there are two constraints. The first constraint is that the risk increased by addition of the new stocks must be such that the total risk of the portfolio after buying remains less than the maximum allowed risk exposure. The second constraint is that the cost of the cheapest stock must be less than or equal to L_T , that is the liquid available at that point of time.

$$L_T \geq \min(E_\Phi) \quad - (Cr. 2)$$

$$R_{allowed} > 0 \quad - (Cr. 3)$$

$$\text{where } R_{allowed} = R_{max} - \mathcal{R}_{k^B}$$

In Cr. 3, \mathcal{R}_{k^B} is the risk exposure of our portfolio before buying in the current time period. For instance, in our example of ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , let the \hat{R} value be $1/3$. Therefore, the R_{max} value comes out to be $\frac{1}{3} \times 460 = 153.33$. Our \mathcal{R}_{k^B} value is the risk exposure from both the stocks and is equal to 138. Hence, $R_{allowed}$ is equal to $153.33 - 138 = 15.33$. Therefore, we can add stocks to our portfolio such that the risk from the added stocks is less than or equal to 15.33. On the other hand, let us assume that at some other time period, the current price C_T of ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 becomes 19 and 15 respectively. Ideally, this type of situation would be avoided due to trend captured prediction but since the current prices are greater than their respective Stoploss values, therefore, the situation is mathematically valid. In this situation, the value of our portfolio is $19 \times 10 + 15 \times 10 = 340$. The R_{max} value at this time period is $\frac{1}{3} \times 340 = 113.33$. Since we have not sold any shares, the \mathcal{R}_{k^B} value remains the same, which is 138. We can see that in this situation the value of $R_{allowed}$ is -24.66 . Therefore, in this time period, even if there are BUY signals pending, the model cannot make a Confirmed BUY trigger because of the risk exposure constraint. Cr. 2 denotes that the available liquid must be greater than or equal to the buying cost of the cheapest stock present in our prelim BUY list.

We prioritize the stocks that have received a prelim BUY signal on the basis of their $\varphi_{\phi_i'}$ values. This $\varphi_{\phi_i'}$ value is the φ_{ϕ_i} of the stock Φ_i calculated from equation 17, divided by the number of shares of Φ_i that is currently present in our portfolio.

$$\varphi_{\phi_i'} = \frac{\varphi_{\phi_i}}{N_{\phi_i(\mathbb{U})}} \quad \text{iff } N_{\phi_i(\mathbb{U})} > 0 \quad - (23)$$

The division by $N_{\phi_i(\mathbb{U})}$ is done while prioritizing because we have an incentive to diversify our portfolio as much as possible. The stocks that have received prelim BUY trigger are then arranged according to their decreasing $\varphi_{\phi_i'}$ values. The stocks are checked for confirmed BUY trigger in this sorted order, with the stock with highest $\varphi_{\phi_i'}$ value checked first.

Let $R_{B(\phi_i)}$ be the risk exposure that we can add in our portfolio from buying shares of stock ϕ_i . Then in the model, the value of $R_{B(\phi_i)}$ is computed as:

$$\frac{R_{B(\phi_i)}}{R_{allowed}} = \frac{EMA_{(Gain(\phi_i))} \times Vol.(\phi_i)}{\sum EMA_{(Gain(\phi_j))} \times Vol.(\phi_j)} \quad - (24)$$

$$R_{B(\phi_i)} = \frac{EMA_{(Gain(\phi_i))} \times Vol.(\phi_i)}{\sum EMA_{(Gain(\phi_j))} \times Vol.(\phi_j)} \times R_{allowed} \quad - (25)$$

In equation 24, $EMA_{(Gain(\phi_i))}$ is the expected EMA gain according to the 3rd degree polynomial curve fit and is given by:

$$\hat{Y}_{EMA(T+n\Delta t)} - \hat{Y}_{EMA(T)} \quad - (26)$$

$Vol.(\phi_i)$ is the volatility of the stock ϕ_i .

Since the model can undertake SELL decision in every time period, therefore, we set $R_{B(\phi_i)}$ directly proportional to $Vol_{(\phi_i)}$ with the intention to invest more in stocks which have higher volatility level.

The number of shares of the stock ϕ_i that can be bought is easily computable using the following formula:

$$N_{\phi_i} = \frac{R_{B(\phi_i)}}{E_{\phi_i} - SL_{U(\phi_i)}} \quad - (27)$$

The value of N_{ϕ_i} has to be greater than or equal to one ($N_{\phi_i} \geq 1$), implying that at least the transaction of one share needs to take place. Another condition is that the amount needed to buy N_{ϕ_i} number of shares must be less than or equal to the available liquid at that point of time. Mathematically it is $E_{\phi_i} \times N_{\phi_i} \leq L_T$. We buy the maximum number of shares of ϕ_i that we possibly can under these constraints.

ALGORITHM 5: Buying Shares Based on Risk

```

Compute  $R_{max}$ 
Compute  $\mathcal{R}_{k B}$ 
Compute  $R_{allowed}$ 
IF  $R_{allowed} > 0$ :
    List = Sort.Desc( $\varphi_{\phi_i}$ )
    FOR ( $i$  in List)
        Compute  $N_{\phi_i}$ 
        IF  $N_{\phi_i} \geq 1$ :
             $Cap_{\phi_i} \approx \frac{L_T}{E_{\phi_i}}$ 
            IF  $Cap_{\phi_i} \geq N_{\phi_i}$ :
                BUY  $N_{\phi_i}$ 
                 $L_T = L_T - (E_{\phi_i} \cdot N_{\phi_i})$ 
            ELSE:
                BUY  $Cap_{\phi_i}$ 
                 $L_T = L_T - (E_{\phi_i} \cdot Cap_{\phi_i})$ 
        ELSE:  $i++$ 
    END FOR

```

In the above algorithm5, we first check if the $R_{allowed}$ value is greater than 0. If it is, then all the stocks that have received prelim BUY signals are sorted in descending order according to their φ_{ϕ_i} values, computed by equation23. We move through the sorted list and in the sorted list, for each of the stocks we check the number of shares we can buy of stock ϕ_i depending on the risk $R_{B(\phi_i)}$. If the number is greater than or equal to 1, then we compute the capacity, which is basically the number of shares of ϕ_i that we can buy based on our current liquid amount. If the capacity is greater than or equal to N_{ϕ_i} , then we buy N_{ϕ_i} number of shares and update the Liquid amount L_T . Likewise, if the capacity is less than N_{ϕ_i} , then we buy all the shares we can afford. In Algo5, line 9, while computing Cap_{ϕ_i} , we are rounding down the value, hence, for example if we get our capacity for a particular stock to be 30.8, then we round down the value to be 30.

5. ALGORITHM FLOWCHART AND DISCUSSIONS

In the previous section, we described the instrumental goals that are required for the proposed model. The step by step execution of the instrumental goals provides us with the following algorithm flowchart.

The flowchart above shows the decision flow for a stock in our model. First the price and the net sentiment for the current time period is fed to the model then the price list and the net sentiment list is updated. These lists hold the most recent n number of elements of prices & net sentiment. The correlation between the price and net sentiment is calculated. If it is less than 0.6, it is deemed to be indeterminable and the model is halted, else the Net Sentiment List is linearly curve fitted. If the R squared value of the curve fit comes out to be less than 0.5, it is deemed indeterminable and model is halted. If the R squared value is greater than or equal to 0.5, we go ahead and compute the φ_{ϕ_i} value of the stock. If φ_{ϕ_i} is positive, a prelim buy signal is thrown while if the value is negative, a prelim sell signal is thrown. This is essentially the first decision branch in the model.

If the prelim Sell state is reached, then we compute the μ value using equation 18. If the computed value is $1 > \mu > 0$, then the model triggers a confirm Sell signal otherwise the model holds the stock for the current time period and the flow is completed. If Sell action takes place, we update the risk exposure value using equation 21 and then the model completes the flow for the time period.

If the prelim Buy state is reached, then we wait and run the above flowchart algorithm for all the stocks to filter the stocks that are receiving a prelim Buy signal. All the stocks are collected in a list data-structure and are sorted according to their φ_{ϕ_i} values. The list is traversed one element at a time. We check the $R_{allowed}$ value and if the value is less than or equal to 0, then we cannot add risk exposure to our portfolio, hence, we cannot buy new shares. If the value is greater than 0, then the liquid constraint is checked ($Cr. 2$), if the condition is not satisfied then again, we cannot buy new shares. If the condition is satisfied, then essentially, we execute algorithm 5. After traversing through the list, the flow is completed for the current time period and the next flow is initiated again in the next time period.

In a same time period, if the model gets multiple SELL signals as well as BUY signals, then the SELL signals are executed first and then only BUY signals are to be executed.

Figure 8

This is done because selling shares of stocks clear out some of the total risk exposure from the portfolio. Therefore, it is necessary to execute the sell phase before

executing the buy phase so that the model is provided with the latest value of $\mathcal{R}_{k B}$, which is used to calculate the $R_{allowed}$ value.

Although the proposed model is based on the fact that various studies have previously shown that share prices can be predicted with a relatively high accuracy using extracted public sentiment towards a company/asset, but there are various challenges that arise when we try to build a general rule-based model which triggers buy/sell signals based on extracted public sentiment. One of which is choosing a reliable source from which public sentiments will be extracted. Another challenge in the model is to add actions for the indeterminable conditions generated. From the algorithm flowchart, it can be seen that there are two such cases where the flow terminates abruptly. Although it can be argued that the condition $R^2(Linear Fit) < 0.5$, may indicate an upcoming trend change in the extracted public sentiment, nevertheless, the model treats the situation as indeterminable. These situations pose a threat to the model as repeated occurrences may render the model useless.

Another issue in the model is that it holds the shares until a Sell signal is given, which may cause the model to miss the opportunity of buying shares of stocks showing higher uptrend potential. This is a direct result of the allowed risk constraint which sets an upper limit on the risk exposure combined with the fact that the model only unloads shares of a stock if and only if a SELL signal is triggered for that stock.

Due to these limitations, we believe that the proposed model, in its current state, needs to be supplemented with other models to handle the pathological conditions and maximize profitability.

6. CONCLUSION

The overwhelming evidence that public sentiment towards a stock can be a useful feature for predicting the stock's price movement demands for algorithmic models that can use this feature for automated trading.

In this paper we proposed a deterministic model that provides BUY or SELL signals by analysing the public sentiment towards a company/stock. The proposed model is designed to act as a central engine for an automated algorithmic trading model. The decision filtering in the model is two-fold in nature, as in, for a particular stock, first a prelim BUY/SELL Signal is generated by analysing public sentiment and then a confirm BUY/SELL signal is generated by studying the price movement of the stock. The proposed model also takes into account the total risk exposure of the portfolio which determines the number of shares to be bought.

Although we have not tested the model in live market, but outcomes from simulation show promising results. There are some flaws in the model that we have already discussed in the previous section and our immediate future work is to improve the model by eliminating the flaws and maximizing the profitability.

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